

Nguyen Trai's Ideological Values Of Tolerance And Solidarity In Building A Consensual, Harmonious, Humane And Compassionate Society In Vietnam Today

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Abstract

Nguyen Trai is a military strategist, politician, diplomat and also a philosopher, a big humanist in the history of Vietnamese thought. Nguyen Trai's thoughts expressed in many fields and have made great contributions to the history of Vietnamese thought. In particular, Nguyen Trai's thought of tolerance and solidarity is not only valid half a millennium ago, but also has modern influences, creating sustainable values and exerting great influence on Vietnam society nowadays. The article focuses on analyzing, interpreting and proving to clarify the basic features of Nguyen Trai's ideological values of tolerance and solidarity in building a consensual, harmonious, humane and compassionate society in Vietnam nowadays.

Introduction

Throughout the history of nation building and defense of the Vietnamese nation, many great thinkers have appeared, including Nguyen Trai. Nguyen Trai's thought is expressed in many fields and has profound humanistic values, especially his thoughts on morality, including those on tolerance and solidarity. These ideas are not only valuable in history, but also have great value for Vietnam today. Vietnam's current context is undergoing many changes, under the influence of many factors such as market economy, globalization, international economic integration, rapid development of information technology, the problem of moral degradation, etc., the research clarifies the values of Nguyen Trai's thought on tolerance and solidarity, not only contributing to affirming the good traditional moral values of the nation, but also making clearly understand more about Nguyen Trai's contributions to the historical ideological flow of the Vietnamese nation and especially draw out the value of that thought with building a humane and benevolent society in the context of international integration is absolutely necessary now.

Research questions:

Question 1: What is the basic content of tolerance and solidarity in Nguyen Trai's ideology?

Question 2: What are Nguyen Trai's ideological values of tolerance and solidarity in building a consensual, harmonious, humane and compassionate society in Vietnam today?

Literature Review

In the article "*Nguyen Trai, a patriot representing the humanity and peaceful will of the Vietnamese people at the beginning of the 15th century*" of the author Minh Tranh (Journal of Literature - History - Geography No. 20, August 1956, 1956) analyzed Nguyen Trai's thought of humanity, thereby showing the relationship between his ideas of patriotism, humanity, people, and peace. In the book "*Nguyen Trai: Genius Cultural and Political*" (Publishing House of Literature - History - Geography 1957), the authors Mai Hanh - Nguyen Dong Chi - Le Trong Khanh said that: moral thought whose focus is on benevolence and righteousness category is the foundation for him to build his political views. Author Bui Van Nguyen with the article "Discussing more about Nguyen Trai's thought of humanity" (Philosophical Review, No. 3, October 1964)" initially pointed out that Nguyen Trai had absorbed the humane thought of Khong Manh and transmitted it to him. our country through the book Tong Nho.

Bui Van Nguyen, Nguyen Trai, (Culture Publishing House 1980). Institute of Literature, Nguyen Trai, the mettle and quintessence of our nation, (Social Science Publishing House 1980). Vietnam Institute of Social Sciences, 600th anniversary of Nguyen Trai's birth" (Social Science Publishing House, 1982). The three works

collect articles by many authors about Nguyen Trai's life and career, emphasizing the thesis that his life is a great example of human morality and has a profound influence on future generations.

Tran Nguyen Viet with two articles: "*Nguyen Trai's humanistic thought in "Quan trung tu menh tap"*" (Philosophy Journal, No. 1 – 2000) and "*About the relationship of the three religions in Nguyen Trai's thought*" (Philosophy Journal, No. No. 7- 2005) highlighted Nguyen Trai's humanistic thought as an interference and connection between the three ideologies of Confucianism - Buddhism - Taoism. The point for Nguyen Trai's life to be more beautiful when he retreated to Con Son to enjoy nature and all things.

In the book "*Contributing to the understanding of Nguyen Trai's philosophical thought*" (National Political Publishing House 2015), the two authors Doan Chinh & Bui Trong Bac emphasized their views on morality, the people, and the nation in Nguyen Trai's thought, thereby stating the values and historical significance of these views. According to the authors, Nguyen Trai left valuable historical lessons for life today, when global problems of the times, especially the risk of war and environmental degradation, are threatening human life. The authors of the book series "*A Brief History of Vietnamese Philosophical Thought*" (Published by National University of Pedagogy 2016): considered Nguyen Trai's concept of morality as the basic foundation on which he built his thesis. other virtues such as patriotism, the spirit of national independence, and love of nature.

The article "*Try to learn about Nguyen Trai's moral concept through Quoc Am Thi Tap*" by author La Kim Lien, published in the journal Literature, issue 4-2004, commented: When reading Nguyen Trai's Quoc Am Thi Tap, we find the moral concept and teachings of Uc Trai very profound and vivid, expressing a new thought that transcends time until today and in the future. The author also said that: all the ethical issues that Nguyen Trai cares about expressed in Quoc Am Thi Tap, the following main points emerge: self-advice and self-advocacy; advise and teach people; Advise and teach children; draw morality for the next generation.

The article "*About Nguyen Trai's humanitarian thought*" by Luong Minh Cu and Nguyen Thi Huong, published in the Philosophical Review No.11 in 2007, said that Nguyen Trai's thought of humanity is a profound philosophy, covered his entire life. The article has analyzed the ideology of humanity in many aspects: benevolence means loving the people, for the people, and keeping the people safe; Humanity means tolerance, generosity; Humanity means the ideal of building a peaceful country. Nguyen Trai's thought of humanity inherits the Confucian view of humanity, but has been expanded and developed more, creating a unique mark in the history of Vietnamese thought.

The article "*About Philosophical Thoughts of Nguyen Trai*", by author Doan Chinh, Philosophy journal, (September 2009 issue) has pointed out the theoretical premise for the formation of Nguyen Trai's philosophical thought. Next, study Nguyen Trai's philosophical thought on three main contents: Nguyen Trai's views on heaven, earth and people; Nguyen Trai's thoughts on humanity, especially ideas about the people and the role of the people; Nguyen Trai's conception of time. Although there are certain points about Nguyen Trai's philosophical thought, the article has not gone into in-depth analysis of each content to be able to cover the entire Nguyen Trai thought.

The two authors Doan Chinh & Bui Trong Bac "*Contributing to understanding Nguyen Trai's philosophical thought*" (National Political Publishing House 2015). In this monograph, the authors have emphasized the views on morality as a human being, the people, and the nation in Nguyen Trai's thought, highlighting thereby the values and historical significance of Nguyen Trai's views. According to the authors, Nguyen Trai has left valuable historical lessons for the contemporary societies, when global problems of the times, especially the danger of war and environmental degradation, pose a considerable threat not only to human life.

Research Method

Studying Nguyen Trai's ideological values of tolerance and solidarity in building a consensual, harmonious, humane and compassionate society in Vietnam today requires an interdisciplinary scientific approach, such as: ethics, Philosophy, Literature, Psychology, Sociology.

In the process of approaching the issue, the authors use research methods such as: Text analysis, logic - history, the unity between synchronic and diachronic perspective, analysis - synthesis, etc. These research methods are applied in a consistent dialectical way by the authors to provide a comprehensive and specific research approach suitable for the task at hand.

Results and Discussion

1. Basic content of tolerance and solidarity in Nguyen Trai's ideology

"Social consensus" is a category appearing with high frequency in the majors of culture, sociology and philosophy in Vietnam in the late twentieth century as a consequence of promoting the spirit of tolerance and solidarity. Author Nguyen Tran Bat said that, "social consensus is first and foremost the result of cognitive consensus. In this day and age, when cooperation becomes a basic philosophical content of modern life, consensus becomes the theory and vision in building the future social structure on all three aspects of economics, politics, culture. In other words, political democracy, economic freedom and

cultural openness are important guarantees of social consensus" (Bat, 2016, p.288). Social consensus is seen as the unification between awareness and social action towards the spirit of cooperation in all aspects of life.

Research by Nguyen Thi Phuong Mai shows that "social consensus is understood in the following main aspects: 1) Consensus among political subjects on a number of basic values and standards that are universally accepted. 2) The adoption of a decision does not require a vote, when there is a general consensus of all" (Mai, 2016, p.15). Such conceptions of social consensus speak to a relatively broad and complete range of the connotations and exteriors of the concept that lies at the boundary between the disciplines of culture, ethics, politics, philosophy and sociology.

In traditional culture, Nguyen Trai viewed consensus as the basis of solidarity, the glue that held the community together, this was described by him in his political essay "Binh Ngo Dai Cao": "Generals and soldiers have a fatherly heart/Mix the water with a cup of sweet wine". Thanks to the joint efforts and unanimity above and below like a father and son in such a family, ten years of arduous resistance have passed and victory has come. The thought of "consensus" reflected in Nguyen Trai's poem has created a historical imprint on the hearts of every Vietnamese people, forming unconscious commands, so that whenever the country has natural calamities and enemy-inflited destruction, that order sends out "SOS signal" to gather the people's strength.

The term "Harmony" commonly used in Vietnamese today is a word "Sino-Vietnamese", so to understand its modern semantics, it is necessary to make a journey back to ancient Chinese culture. In the Sino-Vietnamese book compiled by Phan Van Cac and Lai Cao Nguyen: "Harmony is being well-balanced, satisfactory combination" (Cac & Nguyen, 1989, p.99). When looking in ancient books, Ha Thanh Hien found that "Harmony" is an ancient Chinese musical instrument made of bamboo used to blow, like the flute, the flute in Vietnamese musical instruments today. This means that the origin of the word "Harmony" begins with an ancient musical instrument, here "Harmony" means through the rhythmic harmony of the instrument to achieve the art of sound harmony (Hien, 2010, p. 85). The discovery of the origin of the term "Harmony" in this ancient text means the same as the word "Harmony" recorded in the following text of Nguyen Trai. The old history records that, after King Le Thai To died, the government was in turmoil, society became chaotic and unreligious. Nguyen Trai wrote a letter to King Le Thai Tong with painful words: "Peace is the root of music, sound is the literature of music. Dare to ask Majesty to love and care for all peoples, so that the villages and hamlets will not have a sound of anger and resentment, that is to keep the original music" (History Institute, 2013, p.563).

The word "Harmony" in the above paragraph is nothing but harmony, solidarity, attachment, and tolerance for each other according to the folk motto that Nguyen Trai once portrayed: "Advise everyone to yield, not to quarrel, to be jealous, to be hostile" (Trai, 1976, p.426). Because in the context of society with so many problems to worry about, Nguyen Trai understands that "if we can keep each other in life, everything is good/hard or soft" (Trai, 1976, p.442). People in a country, a nation - a nation are born from the same place and call each other with "compatriots", fighting for political power, material interests, living space is no different from "Birds in their little nests agree".

In the West, the term "harmony" first appeared in the writings of ancient Greco-Roman philosophers, typically the Pythagorean conception, according to which number is the source of all things (number 1 makes up points, number 2 creates a line, number 3 creates a plane, number 4 creates a shape), is the material that creates arithmetic based on the principle of "harmony". The Heraclite philosopher, when propounding the "Logos theory", said that all things in the world exist in unity and struggle with each other. Struggle and unity are two attributes in the same thing, a system, they are indispensable for each other (Su, 2020, p.201). The concept of harmony of the Greek philosophers was developed by the modern German philosopher - Leibnitz in an idealistic direction when he said that all things were formed and developed according to the principle of "preordained harmony", that is, Some invisible "supernatural" force exists before all things, like a grain of rice when it sprouts, it will only become a seedling. This concept has mystical idealism, but it speaks to the aesthetic value of harmony and balance in the structure and function of all things, including society.

The history of the post-Le era proves that throughout his life as a mandarin, Nguyen Trai always pondered and wondered about the answer to the question: What should the head of state and the mandarin system do and how to live forever? people are prosperous, happy, peaceful, live in the prospect of peace? The process of finding the answer to this question has created Nguyen Trai's personality as bright as a star in the sky of Dai Viet at the time with the motto of life "Humanity, sentiment is the core of peace". But in order for the people to be at peace, they must first create a prosperous life, because if the material life is secure, the new social order will be stable. Nguyen Trai once confided that "if you are poor, no one cares about rituals". The situation that troubled him the most in his whole life as a mandarin was the extreme poverty of the people at the time, who worked as farmers but could not plow the fields but had to be soldiers with weapons. That is the reason why, "in order to summon army generals in Nghe An citadel, Tan Binh Thuan Hoa", to encourage the fighting spirit of the insurgents, he

wrote passionate words that moved people's hearts: "I revolted in your land, now I want to succeed, I hope you will stay faithful with one heart, one piece of gold, in order to achieve the righteousness of the army and god father and son... regain the territory... After defeating the enemy, I will divide half of my troops to work in the fields" (Trai, 1976, p.143). Writing so touchingly, because he knew that farming is not only a reason for life, but also a sacred duty, an inherent instinct of every Vietnamese in a wet rice civilization that is "naturally agrarian". Agricultural thinking considers land more precious than gold and silver.

Tolerance and solidarity have become basic and fundamental values to help people get closer together, to understand, share, cooperate and develop together. Tolerance and solidarity are considered as basic means to resolve ethnic conflicts, political differences, ideological struggles and religious diversity on a global scale today. It is a condition for peace, economic development and social progress. Tolerance and solidarity are attitudes, ways of organizing and operating society and the nation, to "build an advanced culture imbued with national identity".

Nguyen Trai's concept of tolerance and solidarity is influenced by many cultural flows, of which Confucianism, Buddhism, and Taoism are the foundation, while the Vietnamese national identity is the mainstream. Studying Nguyen Trai's works, it is possible to generalize his concept of tolerance and solidarity in the following points: *Firstly*, tolerance and solidarity are based on the foundation of humanity, in other words, humanity is the source and core value of tolerance and solidarity. Humanity is the basis, the foundation, the requirement of the way people behave, moreover, humanity is also the principle and standard in dealing with work. Humanity becomes a great spiritual strength, creating the advantage to take the enemy with a few, and defeat the strong with the weak. Humanism means taking the real as the root according to the motto "Only with food can one achieve enlightenment". Humanity becomes the main thread, the content runs through the whole thought of Nguyen Trai. In all circumstances, whether war or peace, he always held up the banner of humanity, considering it as the source and foundation of human morality, the motto of dealing with people in order to win people's hearts and lead the country and the people to a peaceful, prosperous and happy life.

Secondly, tolerance is the source and basis of solidarity, while solidarity is the driving force and strength to promote and strengthen tolerance. According to Nguyen Trai, solidarity among members of a community is like the harmony and harmony between musicians in an orchestra, all instruments must be harmonized and arranged in order for the music to sound smooth. Social life is the same, it is necessary to be in harmony, all for the same purpose, the society is peaceful, because social discord is the risk of disorder.

Thirdly, tolerance and solidarity are associated with peace love and nature-friendly lifestyle. Nguyen Trai believes that living in peace and happiness is the common mentality of all people and the earnest aspiration of all social classes. Because according to him, "the Way of Heaven loves life, people's heart hates instability". Loving peace, condemning war is the message that Nguyen Trai wants to send to posterity with the message that holding weapons is a reluctant job, keep the peace while the opportunity is still there. Reading the two poetry books "Uc Trai Thi Tap" and "Quoc Am Thi Tap" can we see that Nguyen Trai was born to write poetry, not as a politician. Nguyen Trai's poetry contains a great love for nature, with sharp pen and ingenious description, nature and people have a harmonious connection.

2. Nguyen Trai's ideological values of tolerance and solidarity in building a consensual, harmonious, humane and benevolent society in Vietnam today

In order to build a consensus and harmonious society on the basis of inheriting the ideology of tolerance and solidarity of Nguyen Trai, the Party and State of Vietnam under the leadership of President Ho Chi Minh have given the following guidelines:

Firstly, economic development, ensuring social security.

This is not only the acquisition and promotion of Confucianism's thought "the country takes the people as the root, takes the people and cares about the economy" of Confucianism, including the thought of Nguyen Trai but also one of the strategic tasks throughout the process of nation building in Vietnam. To ensure social security, first of all, we must pay attention to the development of human resources, because no matter how modern machines and technology are, they cannot replace human positions. And it is worth noting that people here need to meet modern qualities such as strong physical strength, flexible work, enthusiasm for work, the ability to master modern technology, especially tolerance, solidarity, ignoring differences, towards a spirit of cooperation, forming a synergy for the common development of the community, country and humanity.

To have people with the following qualities: i) Having a sense of responsibility, a high level of culture, a professional level and the ability to master himself, his family and society. ii) Being a laborer of the new society, living with culture, love. iii) Rich in patriotism, love of socialism and imbued with a pure and noble proletarian international spirit, one must pay attention to education, following the motto "For the sake of ten years, we must plant trees, for the sake of 100 years, we should cultivate people" (Minh, 2000, vol.10, p.180). In order to improve the quality of people, Ho Chi Minh attaches great importance to educating the people, because according to him, an ignorant nation is a weak nation, so the eradication of

ignorant enemies is equally important and urgent as defeating foreign invaders. He said that in order for the country's construction to go to success, a revolutionary cadre must first be a leader, exemplary, thrifty, incorruptible, righteous, and impartial. Cadres are not "revolutionary officials" but must really be "servant, public servants" of the people, worried about people's lives, suffering before the world, happy after the world. Ho Chi Minh always emphasized the need to train people comprehensively, develop unity and harmony between the qualities of Humanity - wisdom - courage, between virtue and talent, between pink and professional. In general, Ho Chi Minh's thought about man is the crystallization of the entire concept of religion as a person with tolerance and solidarity as the core in Vietnamese history, on perception, human is a unified entity between biological aspects - social aspects.

In today's life, when production is expanded, international economic groups, transnational companies are formed, production forces and production relations are internationalized, tolerance concept and union is externalized. The content needs to be precise, thereby applying the theory to real life, finding a way out for humanity to overcome the disasters of war, epidemics, and climate change. And obviously, when people are standardized, labor productivity increases, production wealth is abundant - that is the prospect of a sustainable society, moving towards building a harmonious society with a democratic society. meaning, leading to a happy and peaceful life. With that motto of action, the XIII Congress of the Communist Party of Vietnam determined:

“Strongly arouse the patriotic spirit, the will for national self-reliance, the strength of national unity and the aspiration to develop a prosperous and happy country; promote socialist democracy, the synergy of the whole political system and of Vietnam's culture and people, foster the people's strength, improve the quality of human resources, and have a breakthrough mechanism for revenue collection. attract and utilize talents, promote innovation, vigorously apply science and technology, create a strong driving force for rapid and sustainable development” (Communist Party of Vietnam, 2021, vol 1, p.34).

Secondly, promote the spirit of national unity, harmony and reconciliation, closing the past, opening a bright future.

Absorbing the solidarity spirit of national hero Nguyen Trai, Ho Chi Minh confidently said: "Nothing is more precious than the people. There is nothing stronger than the united force of the people" (Minh, 2000, vol.10, p.450). Because reality proves that no matter how easy it is, no matter how difficult it is, the people will finish it. Although living hidden in the same village, the village is deserted, but the people are always talented, intellectual, imaginative and creative people. It is the people who know how to handle all problems, even national affairs, in a simple way, but the noble people in the official place are talented but sometimes can't think of it. Aware of that, Ho Chi Minh always believed in the wisdom and strength of the Vietnamese people in the resistance wars against foreign invaders. He wrote praises for the people's united strength to encourage and encourage them: "Our people have a passionate patriotic spirit. It is a precious tradition of ours. From the past to the present, every time the Fatherland was invaded, that spirit was vibrant, it formed a huge and powerful wave, it surmounted all dangers, difficulties, sell the nation and rob the nation" (Minh, 2000, vol.6, p.171). Thanks to his belief in the strength and solidarity of the people, Ho Chi Minh gathered around him a large social force, attracting many intellectuals and mandarins of the old regime with neutral, even the opposition followed the revolution and contributed a lot of material and financial resources to the resistance war and national construction

Solidarity between religions and among religious people is a typical example of Ho Chi Minh's tolerance and national solidarity. He always considers all religions as a precious spiritual heritage of mankind, because he realizes that all religions are aimed at goodness, beauty, humanity, and moral education for the masses. The person who answered the question "Who are you?" of journalists at home and abroad with sensible words: The doctrine of Confucius has the advantage of cultivating personal morality. The religion of Jesus has the advantage of great compassion. Marxism has the advantage of a dialectical working method. Sun Yat senism has the advantage that the policy is suitable to our country's conditions. Don't Confucius, Jesus, and Sun Yat senism have these common advantages? They all seek happiness for humanity and society. If they were still alive today, I believe that they would live together perfectly as close friends. I tried to be their little student" (Thong, 2004, p.325). According to this concept, all religions, although different in form of expression, are the same in the function of moral education, community association and illusory compensation. That is the reason why Ho Chi Minh's behavior towards religion not only shows the science and art of living, but also contains humanity, tolerance and solidarity.

Ho Chi Minh attaches great importance to the solidarity between religious compatriots (religious) and non-religious compatriots. The content of national unity and harmony of Ho Chi Minh was proven when he outlined the urgent task of: "The colonialists and feudalists implemented the policy of separating the Taoists and non-religious people, in order to easily rule, I want our government to declare: free religion and religious are united" (Minh, 2000, vol.4, p.9) This is shown quite clearly, specifically in the "Letter to the compatriots on the occasion of Christmas" (1946): "All of our compatriots, without division of religion, are closely united, determined to resist, to preserve the motherland, but also to preserve the right to freedom of religion" (Minh,

2000, vol.4, p.490). According to that logical inference, Ho Chi Minh considers the human values of religions as valuable spiritual and cultural heritages, found in religious doctrines and creeds many points of content consistent with socialist ideals. That is the reason why, in the line of great national unity, the unity of religions is always a top priority. This humanistic ideology remains valid both in theory and practice in the "all people unite" campaign that our Party and State are promoting today.

The idea of great national unity that Ho Chi Minh raised is the result of a long process of research and reflection on the national tradition of nation building and defending the country, including Nguyen Trai's spirit of solidarity, and at the same time, the The product summarizes valuable experiences through the practical revolutionary struggle of the Vietnamese people and the people of the world. From practical movements, it can be said that the great unity of the whole people is the red thread that runs through and forms the basic content of the Vietnamese revolution. With short sayings and clauses, easy to penetrate into the public's mind "Unity, solidarity, great solidarity, success, success, great success"; "Unity is strength"; "With the unity of the people, anything can be accomplished."

Absorbing Ho Chi Minh's thought, in the process of leading the revolution, the Communist Party of Vietnam has always paid attention to the spirit of tolerance and national unity. With the motto of taking the art of tolerance as the social essence and spiritual support for solidarity and creating the basis and motivation for gathering people's strength, the Document of the 12th National Congress of the Party affirms that: "Respect for differences that are not contrary to the common interests of the nation; uphold the national spirit, patriotic tradition and tolerance to gather and unite with all Vietnamese at home and abroad" (Communist Party of Vietnam, 2016, p.158).

Over the past two decades, thanks to an open policy to call for investment, Vietnam has attracted a large number of overseas Vietnamese businessmen and intellectuals to the country to consult, invest in economic development, science, and education. According to the "Online Finance Magazine", at a dialogue forum between the Ho Chi Minh City government and overseas Vietnamese businesses in the area just held, the representative of the "Committee on Overseas Vietnamese" at Ho Chi Minh City said that in recent years, the wave of overseas Vietnamese returning to visit their homeland and investing in startups is increasing. In the Ho Chi Minh City area alone, every year, about 30,000 Vietnamese people visit their homeland, seeking business opportunities mainly through economic projects. Not only that, with the nature of helping relatives, families, and villages, the amount of money remitted to Vietnam is increasing. According to the State Bank of Vietnam, in the first 10 months of 2020, the amount of remittances transferred to Ho Chi Minh City is estimated at about 3.8 billion USD, mainly from the US market (60%), European countries (19%), the rest are from other countries. At present, statistics from the Ministry of Finance show that the proportion of remittances flowing into the production and business sector accounts for about 70-72%, while about 22% is invested in the field of buying and selling, sell real estate, the rest is used to donate, help, support relatives, do social charity (Ministry of Finance, 2021).

At a time when the state budget and capital are still facing many difficulties today, overseas Vietnamese entrepreneurs and intellectuals return to their homeland to invest in creating leading "native capitalist" businesses such as Techcombank, Vpbank, Vingroup, Eurowindow, Masan, My Lan Chemical Company, Sun Group..., have made important contributions to job creation, vocational training, technology transfer, and local socio-economic development and increase revenue for the state budget.

One thing to be proud of is that when Vietnamese people go abroad to do business, they work hard to study, produce and do business, so most of them become prosperous, accumulate a lot of capital, and make practical contributions to the development of the country. Statistics from the Ministry of Foreign Affairs show that, at present, there are over 4.5 million overseas Vietnamese, living in 110 countries and territories, of which over 500,000 have university degrees, many who is a leading expert in science - technology - economy - finance, even some people have initially joined the political system of countries (such as German deputy chancellor - Philip Roesler). Every year, about 400-500 people come to participate in science and technology activities in Vietnam. The presence of 4 Vietnamese businessmen - intellectuals abroad among the 15 members of the "Prime Minister's Economic Advisory Group" has created momentum for overseas Vietnamese intellectuals to contribute more to the cause. national construction and development (Vietnamese Ministry of Foreign Affairs, 2021). Although the statistics may not be complete, these are really "living and impressive numbers" that reflect the policy of national harmony and reconciliation of the Party and State of Vietnam based on the spirit of peace and and national unity, opening up a bright future, towards the purpose of building a rich and beautiful Vietnam.

Thirdly, build a consensus society, develop harmoniously, humanely, and benevolently.

A humane and benevolent society is humanity's "age-old" dream since its presence on earth to this day. It was the sages and gentlemen, the founders of religions such as Confucius, Shakyamuni Buddha, and Jesus who spoke of the universal world, in which people live according to the principle of "Virtuous people often love people ", "Benevolence – Mercy – Cheerfulness - Indifference", "Love others as love yourself". By the middle of the nineteenth century, Marx and Engels had developed the concept of "scientific socialism", promoting economic justice, political freedom, cultural development - science and

technology, and building a society. humane and benevolent association on the principle of "One for all, all for one" and comprehensive human development. Returning to the nation's past, we see that in his life and creative career, Nguyen Trai has always been nostalgic and dreamed of a humane and benevolent society, in which "all over the village, the neighborhood absent, not a word of resentment".

During the leadership process, the Communist Party of Vietnam has always been interested in creating a humane and benevolent society, in which humanity is the foundation. Building a humane and benevolent society cannot be realized while the people are still hungry, so first of all, it is necessary to conceive of socialism in a really simple way and strive to achieve it, and then propose higher and more ideal goals: "Building socialism is to make society no longer exploit people, no longer hunger and cold, and everyone is well fed and happy" (Minh, 2000, vol.9, p.447). That is the reason why, for nearly a century after independence, the Vietnamese people, despite both resistance war and national construction, have achieved many remarkable achievements towards a society that develops in harmony between the purposes of economic development and economic development. economy and build a new lifestyle, protect cultural identity, preserve green, clean and beautiful living environment.

In the current conditions, Vietnam and the world are facing many advantages and many difficulties, the spirit of tolerance and solidarity continues to be emphasized. The "Document of the 10th National Party Congress" defines: "Upholding the tradition of humanity and tolerance, building a spirit of openness and mutual trust for political stability and social consensus" (Communist Party of Vietnam, 2006, p.116). The spirit of tolerance and solidarity as the fulcrum for political stability of the Communist Party of Vietnam has been continuously aroused and developed. The document of the 11th National Congress of the Communist Party of Vietnam continues to define: "Take the goal of building a peaceful, independent, democratic, fair and civilized Vietnam as a similarity point; remove guilt and prejudice about the past, class composition, accept differences that are not contrary to the common interests of the nation, the tradition of benevolence, tolerance, etc., in order to gather and unite everyone into the face of the nation. joint battle, strengthening social consensus" (Communist Party of Vietnam, 2011, p.239).

In today's society, humanity in general, and Vietnam in particular are facing natural disasters, epidemic diseases are raging and are at risk of spreading more fiercely, historical floods in the central region have recently happened, the current Covid - 19 epidemic is an example. In such general difficult situations of the country, tolerance, solidarity, and attachment among individuals in the community are even more evident through voluntary charity shipments on the principle of "The good leaves cover the ripped ones". People all over the country look to the Central region, towards the beloved "covid-19 epidemic" regions to share the loss of people and property. The free rice ATMs, the free meals, the relief packages... although the material value is still small, it shows the immense generosity of the people that history has proven to be born. from the same egg bag, reflecting the spiritual values of mutual affection and mutual love that have been summed up in the simple philosophy of "The good leaves cover the ripped ones ", "A stitch in time saves nine", "Love grows by giving. The love we give away is the only love we keep" left by his father from time immemorial.

In the context that countries around the world are using all their human and financial resources to fight the epidemic of this century, to encourage the national spirit, create confidence and revolutionary optimism for the people, General Secretary Nguyen Phu Trong in the article "Some theoretical and practical issues about socialism and the path to socialism in Vietnam" affirmed: "We need a society in which development is really for people, not for profit that exploits and tramples on human dignity. We need economic development to go hand in hand with progress and social justice, not widening the gap between rich and poor and social inequality. We need a society of compassion, solidarity, mutual assistance, towards progressive and humane values" (Trong, 2021). These are really timely words of encouragement to the entire people, promoting the spirit of revolutionary optimism for each cadre and party member at a time when life is temporarily calmed down due to the impact of the epidemic.

However, it should also be noted that, in addition to promoting the traditional values of tolerance and solidarity to build a consensual, harmonious, humane and compassionate society, in Vietnam today there are still extreme phenomena, extremists tend to divide the nation, conceptions of life and lifestyle that only know for themselves but lack tolerance and compassion, many interest groups appear and are using all means to implement group interests (Ha, 2011), narrow-minded localism and many vices, and many other negative phenomena worthy of condemnation. Studying this complex contemporary issue from a sociological point of view, based on basic categories such as "tolerance", "compassion", "forbearance", sociological research Phan Tan proposes that it is necessary to build a tolerant society - a society "in which each individual can locate himself in his or her own social organization or group; each organization, social group is built for a responsible, democratic, transparent society, people know how to harmonize interests between individuals and the community. Every citizen, every leader and manager must be held accountable for non-standard behaviors, the culture of shame, the culture of responsibility and the culture of resignation is expressed as a reason to live alongside the values. other everyday

culture” (Tan, 2019, vol 2, 279). If the whole Party and the people were united and determined to do so, surely the purpose of building a harmonious socialist society would get closer and closer, the awareness of socialism would be matured. more fully so as to adjust the theory to the vivid reality that is changing day by day.

Conclusion

Nguyen Trai lives more than half a millennium away from us, but his soul, thought, attitude, and way of dealing with people seem to be present, accompanying the Vietnamese people. This proves that the Nguyen mandarin who worked all his life in the Le Dynasty had a foresight beyond the narrow, conservative feudal ideology of his time. Putting aside the ordinary and private material interests, he integrated with the vast soul of the public according to the life principle of "Keeping cool/calm is to cope with multi-unexpected changes, because they are self-centered" (Taken for granted). the unchanging (the end) to deal with the change (the means), taking the hearts of sentient beings as our own). During his whole life, from his childhood until his success, as a first-ranking official of the court, he still kept an iron heart, loyal to the country, filial piety to the people, loved peace, lived in harmony with nature. But what he wrote is imbued with human love, has a beautiful humanity, and directs people to three eternal values: Truthfulness, Compassion, and Beauty. He is not only beautiful in personality, tolerant towards those who have gone astray, noble in dealing with enemies, but also sublimate in artistic creation, shining on prose and poetry.

As a world cultural celebrity, national liberation hero - Nguyen Trai's life and career has crystallized into valuable historical lessons, in which tolerance and solidarity are core human values - That value has continued to shine in Vietnamese culture for a long time. Nguyen Trai goes down in history deeply in the minds of every Vietnamese person as a lifelong wise man admonishing the people to do good and fight for an independent nation and a peaceful world.

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